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Review Article

An Overview of Efficacy of Cilnidipine over Amlodipine in Renoprotective and Blood Pressure Lowering in the Hypertension with Chronic Disease Patients

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is a medical condition it is characterized by elevated blood pressure in arteries due to high pressure it becomes harder for heart to pump this can ultimately leads to stroke, myocardial infarction, chronic kidney disease, and heart failure. Hypertension is a major risk factor for progression of kidney function, resulting in end-stage renal disease (ESRD). CKD in return, has an adverse effect on blood pressure and may leads to refractory hypertension and along with increased in proteinuria. The blood pressure can reduce the progression of the CKD and also cardiovascular risk. Calcium-channel blockers (CCBs) were considered first-line medication for both hypertension and CKD patients as they being potent vasodilators, are particularly effective in reducing peripheral resistance. Among the CCB's comparison between the cilnidipine and amlodipine, cilnidipine shows the more additional therapeutical effect in decreasing of blood pressure along with proteinuria when compared with amlodipine which is mandatory in hypertension with CKD patients. Amlodipine acts on L-type calcium channel to reduce the blood pressure but it also increases the intraglomerular pressure causing the peripheral oedema where cilnidipine acts on both L-type and N-type calcium channel it helps to reduces the blood pressure by decrease the peripheral resistance and also reduces the intraglomerular pressure that helps to in reduction of peripheral oedema respectively by resisting sympathetic activity which leads inhibition of release of nor-epinephrine. These article explains the effective drug of choice in CCB's. Among amlodipine and cilnidipine, cilnidipine has more incidence in reducing proteinuria than amlodipine.

INTRODUCTION

Hypertension is an medical condition which is characterized as the higher blood pressure in the

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arteries due to the higher blood pressure it becomes difficult for a heart to pump this can lead to other diseases like chronic kidney disease (CKD), and cardiovascular diseases. Hypertension is the major health issue in the south Asia. The main risk factor in hypertension is chronic kidney disease (CKD), myocardial infarction and congestive heart failure if the hypertension is untreated it may lead to end stage renal disease. (an estimated glomerular filtration rate [eGFR] < 60 mL/min/1.73 m²) or kidney damage (often indicated by hint of proteinuria) for ≥ 3 months duration. As eGFR is reduced the hypertension is increased. Previously CKD classification is based on the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) Only. but now proteinuria or the amount of albuminuria is also incorporated. Controlling The blood pressure can reduce the progression of the CKD and also cardiovascular risk. Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is gradually increasing prevalent condition all around the world and is strongly associated with cardiovascular disease (CVD) hypertension acts as both the cause and effect of the chronic kidney disease

RAAS profoundly active at the night time thus the ambulatory BP monitoring is possible to monitor bp at the time.

In this study CCB plays an important role in the hypertensive with CKD patients:

Calcium-channel blockers (CCBs) were considered first-line treatment for hypertension with chronic kidney disease patients. CCB act as vasodilators which are effective in reducing the peripheral resistance. Dihydropyridines like

amlodipine, nifedipine, and felodipine are currently the most frequently used CCBs. Cilnidipine is a dihydropyridines group which is responsible for inhibiting both L and N-type calcium channels that are present on peripheral nerve endings inhibiting calcium release in sympathetic nerves by inhibiting the releasing of norepinephrine (NE). Renal ischemia will cause further sympathetic activation, releasing pressor substances, such as NE and renin, leading to more serious hypertension. Therefore, hypertension and CKD can cause mutual deterioration, and the therapeutic outcomes of hypertension are closely related to renal function.

STAGES OF CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE:

CKD Stage	eGFR Result	Interpretation
Stage 1	90 or higher	Mild kidney damage
Stage 2	60 to 89	Mild kidney damage
Stage 3 a	45 to 59	Mild to moderate kidney damage
Stage 3 b	30 to 44	Moderate to severe kidney damage
Stage 4	15 to 29	Severe kidney damage
Stage 5	Under 15	Kidney failure

CONDITIONS OF HYPERTENSION:

Hypertensive type	Bp range Systole/ diastole (mm of Hg)
Normal	90 or higher
Elevated	120-129/<80
Stage 1	130 -139/80-89
Stage 2	Least 140/90
Hypertensive crisis	Above 180/120
Gestational hypertension	≥140/90

Parameters:	Cilnidipine	Amlodipine
Drug class	Dihydropyridine CCB (blocks L & N-type calcium channels)	Dihydropyridine CCB (blocks L-type calcium channels)

Major Risk Factors	Bradycardia Palpitations Hypotension Advanced aortic stenosis Severe hepatic impairment	Cardiogenic shock Advanced aortic stenosis Severe hepatic impairment Hypersensitivity
Common ADRs	Headache Dizziness Flushing Peripheral oedema (less common than amlodipine)	Peripheral oedema (very common) Headache Flushing Fatigue Palpitations
Less Common ADRs	Gingival hyperplasia Nausea Tachycardia	Gingival hyperplasia Abdominal pain Nausea Rash
Serious ADRs (Rare)	Severe hypotension Worsening angina (rare)	Severe hypotension Myocardial infarction (rare, at initiation) Worsening angina
Oedema Risk	Lower incidence due to N-type blockade reducing sympathetic activity	Higher incidence due to preferential arteriolar dilation
Reflex Tachycardia	Less common	More common compared to cilnidipine

MANAGEMENT OF HYPERTENSION WITH CKD PATIENTS BY ANTI-HYPERTENSIVE DRUGS

1. **ACE Inhibitors (ACEi):** captopril, lisinopril
2. **Angiotensin II Receptor Blockers (ARBs):** Losartan, valsartan
3. **Calcium Channel Blockers (CCBs):** amlodipine, cilnidipine, nifedipine
4. **Diuretics:** Furosemide, hydrochlorothiazide

The most commonly used therapeutic mineralocorticoid is fludrocortisone, while others include aldosterone, deoxycorticosterone acetate (DOCA), and desoxycortone.

DRUG PROFILES:

CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS

Calcium channel blockers (CCBs) are one of the primary class of cardiovascular drugs that exert their therapeutic effects (lowering blood pressure,

reduce heart rate, etc) by inhibiting voltage-gated calcium channels, primarily the L-type channels, in cardiac and smooth muscle cells.

IMPORTANT ROLES OF CALCIUM INFLUX

- Excitation–contraction coupling
- Regulation of vascular tone
- Myocardial contractility
- Atrioventricular conduction.

CCBs reduce intracellular calcium concentrations, leading to vasodilation, decreased myocardial oxygen demand, and modulating the cardiac electrical activity (i.e ECG)

CCBs reduce intercellular calcium concentrations

↓
Vasodilation

↓
Decreased myocardial oxygen demand, modulating the cardiac electrical activity

CLASSIFICATION OF CALCIUM CHANNEL BLOCKERS

Types of Calcium Channels and Calcium Channel Blockers Acting on them

1. Calcium channels are the transmembrane proteins that regulate the entry of calcium ions (Ca^{2+}) into cells.
2. Calcium channel blockers primarily targets on voltage-gated calcium channels.
3. Calcium channel blockers primarily target L-type calcium channels, while newer drug in dihydropyridines such as cilnidipine additionally inhibit N-type channels, contributing to managing the hemodynamic and reno-protective effects.
4. Calcium Channels broadly classified into

Channel Type	Location	Role	CCBs
L-type	Heart, vessels	Contraction, conduction	Amlodipine, Verapamil, Diltiazem
N-type	Sympathetic nerves	NE release	Cilnidipine
T-type	SA node, vessels	Pacemaker activity	Efonidipine
P/Q-type	CNS	Neurotransmission	None
R - type	CNS	Neural firing	None

MECHANISM OF ACTION:

Amlodipine:

1. Usually acts on L-type calcium channel blocker (CCB)
2. Vasodilates mainly peripheral and renal afferent arterioles
3. It leads to increase in the intraglomerular pressure, potentially imbalance between oncotic and hydrostatic pressure it Worsen the proteinuria (protein loss) over the time.

Cilnidipine:

1. It's a dual L- and N-type calcium channel blocker
2. N-type blockade reduces sympathetic nerve activity (release of Nor-epinephrine)
3. Dilates both efferent and afferent arterioles by lowering the hydrostatic pressure within the glomerular capillary that lowers intraglomerular pressure.
4. Leads to better proteinuria reduction and potential renal protection.

Pharmacokinetics:

Cilnidipine is lipophilic drug where it's been administered orally. As it's a first-pass metabolism its bioavailability found to be approximately 13–24%. It reaches the maximum plasma concentration within 1-3 hours. It extensively metabolised in the liver mainly by the CYP3A4 enzyme and forms inactive metabolites. Elimination half-life about 7-8 hours but it maintains the anti-hypertensive effect about 24 hours. It excretes mainly via faeces and small amount is excreted via urine.

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS:

Efficacy:

1. Hypertension associated with CKD worsens renal outcomes and increases cardiac risk. CCB are frequently used when RAAS inhibitors alone are inadequate.
2. Amlodipine [L-Type CCB] significantly reduces systemic BP and enhances cardiac outcomes. Mainly, it dilates afferent arteries, which could worsen pressure within the glomerulus and has little impact on proteinuria.
3. Cilnidipine [L and N-Type CCB] shows comparable reduction in BP and loss of protein while reducing sympathetic activation via N-Type CCB suppression. This triggers to decreased intraglomerular pressure between afferent arterioles and efferent venules that result in significantly lowering in proteinuria, a crucial outcome measure in CKD.

Clinical studies suggest that cilnidipine is not worse than amlodipine in BP regulation and more effective in renoprotection

Safety profile and ADRs:

1. Peripheral oedema, a common ADR with amlodipine, is especially difficult in CKD patients.
2. Cilnidipine's dual mechanism decreases venous resistance, reducing oedema prevalence and improving safety.

Sr. No	Marker	Amlodipine	Cilnidipine
1.	Peripheral oedema	Frequent	Considerably low
2.	Reflex tachycardia	Potential	Low

3.	Headache	Frequent	Lower Incidence
4.	Increasing Proteinuria	Potential	Uncommon
5.	Overall Safety Profile	Medium	Superior

Drug Interactions:

1. These drugs are metabolised via cytochrome P450 3A4
2. Combined use with effective CYP3A4 inhibitors, can enhance plasma levels.
3. Both are well tolerated when used with ARBs or ACE inhibitors, a standard treatment in CKD.
4. Cilnidipine demonstrates fewer significant drug interaction -related adverse reactions in CKD patients.

Cost Effectiveness:

1. Amlodipine is cost-effective and globally available, reducing costs for chronic BP regulation.
2. Cilnidipine, although more expensive, could be cost-effective in CKD due to:
 - Lesser proteinuria
 - Lower oedema
 - Improved patient adherence

Patient Adherence:

1. These two agents allow for daily dosing, enhancing adherence.
2. Amlodipine stoppage is prevalent due to swelling

3. Patients with CKD show higher compliance with cilnidipine due to

- Reduced swelling discomfort
- Better heart rate regulation

Special populations:

CKD Elderly patients:

1. Effective in both.
2. Cilnidipine indicated when swelling or orthostatic effects appear.

Renal Impairment:

1. No dose modification needed for early stage of CKD.
2. Cilnidipine delivers added renal protection action.
3. Dose carefully indicated for both, due to liver breakdown.

Comparison of Guideline Recommendations

Guidelines	Amlodipine	Cilnidipine
JSH 2019[Japan]	Effective in reducing blood pressure but lower efficacy in the reduction of proteinuria.	Recommended in proteinuria positive CKD patients because of N-Type voltage gated calcium channel suppression and reduction of sympathetic activity.
WHO 2021	Suggested, incorporated or recognized into the WHO model list of essential drugs.	Not recorded in WHO essential medicines list, not widely available globally.

Clinical Focus	Enhanced BP control, commonly available, known safety record.	Renal protective, decreases proteinuria, effective in CKD advancement.
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DISCUSSION:

Hypertension with chronic kidney disease (CKD) significantly induces the renal and cardiac complications. To optimize it, drug of choice must be more efficient in comparing within CCBs. In comparison between amlodipine and cilnidipine both the drugs efficiently reduces blood pressure and regulating the heart rate efficiently by regulating blocking of L- type channel. However cilnidipine has a dual action by regulating blocking L- type and N- type calcium channel that results by inhibiting the sympathetic nerve action leading to potentially reduction of intraglomerular pressure and proteinuria.

Amlodipine majorly shows the therapeutic effect to reduce the blood pressure and sustained bp but more frequently associated with increasing in intraglomerular pressure leading to cause of pedal oedema.

Overall, both amlodipine and cilnidipine has an efficient to lower the blood pressure and regulating the heart rate, but cilnidipine has an additional therapeutic effect i.e renoprotection which is mandatory for the patients who are suffering from hypertension with chronic kidney disease.

CONCLUSION:

Both amlodipine and cilnidipine are effective antihypertensive agents, capable of decreasing the blood pressure and heart rate. Amlodipine is widely used because of its proven efficacy in reducing hypertension but some patients respond better to it than to cilnidipine. Cilnidipine, however offers additional benefits as it's a dual

action N- and L-type calcium channel blocking mechanism particularly in reducing proteinuria, enhances renal protection. Consequently, cilnidipine is often preferred for hypertensive patients with renal impairment, providing comprehensive management of the heart rate, blood pressure, and kidney health, potentially leading to better long-term clinical outcomes.

Future Perspectives

Despite the extensive use of amlodipine and cilnidipine in managing high blood pressure, various aspects are yet to be investigated to more clearly establish their long-term therapeutic uses. Current research shows similar reducing blood pressure effects, however new data indicates possibilities additional benefits with cilnidipine because of its L and N-Type calcium channel inhibition.

Potential New Indications:

Cilnidipine is being extensively explored to:

- Hypertension with CKD patients because of its proteinuria-reducing effects.
- Hypertension-related diabetes, where sympathetic suppression may afford metabolic benefits.
- Patients with elevated SNS activity or tachycardia, where reflex tachycardia is undesirable effect.

Amlodipine, simultaneously persists at high levels in combination therapies for uncontrolled hypertension and cardiovascular risk lowering.

Precision Medicine and Genomics:

Advances in genetic based therapy can assist in identifying patients who may benefit more from

N-Type calcium channel inhibition, facilitating the path for patient-specific hypertension therapy. Ongoing research is needed to link genetic markers with therapeutic response and adverse effect profiles.

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